

Practice Abstract no. 31

Restaurant recommendation systems

(Updated for 2025)

Poor nutrition is a critical modern health problem, strongly linked to non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, and cancer [1, 2].

As general and population-wide diets often fail due to individual characteristics and responses, personalised and precision nutrition (based on genetic and lifestyle factors) are essential, particularly for those with chronic conditions.

Advancing personalised nutrition increasingly relies on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). These technologies power recommendation systems by recognising food and ingredients, and can also be used for disease detection [3]. To make these systems work, large individual health datasets must be collected, including metrics such as heart rate and body fat.

This Practice Abstract addresses Restaurant Recommendation Systems, one of several recommenders in personalised nutrition. As seen in a first version of the practice abstract (PA no. 8) about restaurant recommendation systems, this is still a somewhat novel field, with limited research developed.

One of the more recent researched features explored for restaurant recommendation systems was the “meals-plate cycle” framework, which enhances the dining experience by helping users select appropriate plates for their meals. This system uses ML techniques for plate shape estimation and text classification, drawing from datasets on recipe platforms and e-commerce websites to create meal-to-plate pairings that align with user preferences and the characteristics of both the dishes and plates. The limited research in this field suggests significant opportunities for innovation in restaurant recommendation systems. [4]

References

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